

Deliverable D1.1

Project Title:	Building data bridges between biological and medical infrastructures in Europe	
Project Acronym:	BioMedBridges	
Grant agreement no.:	284209	
	Research Infrastructures, FP7 Capacities Specific Programme; [INFRA-2011-2.3.2.] "Implementation of common solutions for a cluster of ESFRI infrastructures in the field of "Life sciences"	
Deliverable title:	Website	
WP No.	1	
Lead Beneficiary:	1: EMBL	
WP Title	Management	
Contractual delivery date:	31 December 2012	
Actual delivery date:	31 December 2012	
WP leader:	Janet Thornton	1: EMBL
Contributing partner(s):	n/a	

Authors: Stephanie Suhr

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1 Executive summary

As detailed in the Description of Work of the BioMedBridges project, there are two different aspects to the provision of a project website: to provide a public face for the project and to serve as a management tool for the provision of internal information to the project partners. Following the examination of these needs it was decided that the most efficient approach is to provide two separate sites or communication channels for these different sets of audiences: project partners and the public.

This deliverable contributes to a large number of the WP1 objectives. First and foremost the deliverable makes a large contribution towards the provision of good and efficient communication between all partners. Good communication will be an essential part of successful management of this complex project throughout its duration.

Especially meetings of the Executive Steering Committee and the Technical Coordination Committee are made significantly more efficient by making all necessary meeting documentation available and easily accessible to all project partners. In addition, due to the set up of the project management website, the respective committee members can get an overview of the overall project, including progress in the work packages, at any time (see details below).

Although not directly affected by the website, objectives 5-8 (reporting to Commission; development of project-wide metrics and – later in the project – a sustainability plan; ethics issues) are also facilitated by the project management website through its provision of complete and accessible information and documentation as well as interactive features such as wikis.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Manage the BioMedBridges project from Year 1-4	x	
2	Organise the management meetings for all the project including: the Annual General Meeting for all partners; the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum)	x	
3	Organise the Scientific Advisory Committee and their annual meeting, including reporting back to all partners	x	
4	Provide good communication between all partners, through a professional web site	x	
5	Ensure timely and appropriate reporting to the commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages		x
6	Develop metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community		x
7	Develop with all partners a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project, following completion of the grant		x
8	Ensure that ethics issues are addressed		x

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Following an examination of the communication needs within and outside of the project it became apparent that there are two or even three separate aims and needs for a “BioMedBridges website”:

1. a website for outreach and to provide public information about the project
2. a site for project management, internal communication between the partners, and document management
3. and, for technical reasons possibly separate from number 1 above, a site for all services and tools developed by the project.

Both the internal site and the site listing the tools and services developed by the project should be linked to the main project website.

To accommodate these different aims in an effective manner that is compatible with the user needs, two sites have been set up:

- www.biomedbridges.eu - the main website with general information about the project, its aims, deliverables and context
- a collaborative site in the content management application Alfresco where partners can exchange documents, information, schedules, and interact in the form of wikis and by other means (hereafter called “project management website”).

A third domain for the tools and services, which will be linked from the outward-facing main project website, is under development.

3.3 Site details

3.3.1 External website www.biomedbridges.eu

The site www.biomedbridges.eu is the external “face of the project”.

- The site is set up in Drupal and hosted by EBI
- The content will eventually be provided and updated by the outreach work package
- It includes for example: news, an overall project description, WP descriptions, and project deliverables (see Figure 1Figure 2Figure 3)

- As the project progresses the site will be used increasingly to publicise the project and to showcase and explain the tools and services developed
- It will provide a “portal” to all bioinformatics tools and services developed by the project, as well as linking to related projects and services.

BioMedBridges [HOME](#) [PARTNERS](#) [WORK PACKAGES](#) [ABOUT](#) [CONTACT](#) [LOG IN](#)

Building data bridges from biology to medicine in Europe

BioMedBridges is a joint effort of ten biomedical sciences research infrastructures on the ESFRI roadmap. Together, the project partners will develop the shared e-infrastructure—the technical bridges—to allow interoperability between data and services in the biological, medical, translational and clinical domains and thus strengthen biomedical resources in Europe.

Find out more about...

- the aims of BioMedBridges
- the structure of the project
- the biomedical sciences research infrastructures and the ESFRI roadmap
- the tasks of the BioMedBridges work packages
- working for BioMedBridges (position openings)
- BioMedBridges publications
- projects, initiatives or organisations related to BioMedBridges
- ...and BioMedBridges on other websites.

NEWS

The first BioMedBridges Knowledge Exchange Workshop, "Practical Solutions with Ontologies", will be held at EMBL-EBI on 4-5 March 2013. Find details [here](#).

BioMedBridges has been highlighted in the 2011 Activity Report on Research and Innovation of the European Commission.

The e-IRG "Blue Paper on Data Management 2012" features BioMedBridges as one of several pilot studies.

The BioMedBridges project is funded by the European Commission within Research Infrastructures of the FP7 Capacities Specific Programme, grant agreement number 284209

The BioMedBridges project website is maintained by the External Services team at the [European Bioinformatics Institute](#)

Figure 1 Front page www.biomedbridges.eu

 BioMedBridges

[HOME](#) [PARTNERS](#) [WORK PACKAGES](#) [ABOUT](#) [CONTACT](#) [LOG IN](#)

Work packages

Work package no.	Title	Activity type	Lead partner
WP1	Management	MGT	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
WP2	Outreach and inreach	COORD	Stichting VU-VUmc
WP3	ESFRI BMS Standards Description and Harmonization	RTD	Karolinska Institutet
WP4	Technical Integration	RTD	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
WP5	Secure access	RTD	Heinrich Heine Universität Düsseldorf
WP6	Use case: Interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales	RTD	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
WP7	Use case: PhenoBridge - crossing the species bridge between mouse and human	RTD	Helmholtz Zentrum München
WP8	Use case: Personalized Medicine - integrating complex data sets to understand disease pathogenesis and improve biomarker and treatment selection	RTD	University of Helsinki, Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland
WP9	Use case: From cells to molecules - integrating structural data	RTD	Science and Technology Facilities Council
WP10	Use case: Integrating disease related data and terminology from samples of different types	RTD	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
WP11	Technology Watch	RTD	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
WP12	Training	COORD	European Molecular Biology Laboratory

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The BioMedBridges project website is maintained by the External Services team at the [European Bioinformatics Institute](#)

Figure 2 List of Work Packages on www.biomedbridges.eu

WP1 - Management

Activity type: MGT

Lead partner:

[European Molecular Biology Laboratory](#)

Work package leader:

[Janet Thornton](#)

Objectives:

- Manage the BioMedBridges project from Year 1-4
- Organise the management meetings for the entire project including: the Annual General Meeting for all partners; the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per year) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per year)
- Organise the Scientific Advisory Committee and their annual meeting, including reporting back to all partners
- Provide good communication between all partners, through a professional web site
- Ensure timely and appropriate reporting to the commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages
- Develop metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community
- Develop with all partners a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project, following completion of the grant
- Ensure that ethics issues are addressed

Description:

The project is coordinated by Professor Janet Thornton at EMBL-EBI on behalf of [ELIXIR](#). The management structure consists of an Executive Steering Committee, made up of the coordinators of the individual ESFRI BMS projects, and a Technical Coordination Committee. Janet Thornton chairs both committees. The Technical Coordination Committee reports to the Coordinator and Executive Steering Committee on a regular basis.

Partners

[EMBL](#)

[UOXF](#)

[KI](#)

[STFC](#)

[HMGU](#)

[VUMC](#)

Documents

No documents available to view for this workpackage

Deliverables

Deliverable no	Title	Lead partner	Due month	Status
1.1	Website	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	12	Ongoing
1.2	Devise Metrics to measure progress and impact of construction	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	12	Completed
1.3	1st Periodic Report	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	18	
1.4	2nd Periodic Report	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	36	
1.5	Final Report & Sustainability Plan	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	48	
1.6	ED1: The Ethical Governance Framework for BioMedBridges	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	18	Ongoing
1.7	ED2: Progress of Compliance with Requirements of the Ethics Review Report	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	36	
1.8	ED3: External Independent Ethics Advisors Report	European Molecular Biology Laboratory	48	

Figure 3 Detailed Work Package description on www.biomedbridges.eu

3.3.2 Content management/collaboration

The content management/collaboration or project management site is intended to facilitate internal communication.

- The site is set up in Alfresco and hosted by EBI
- It provides professional document and content management (e.g. meeting minutes, reports, project information, etc.) and interactive features such as wikis, blogs, commenting and collaborative document editing
- Users (with appropriate authorisations or “roles”) can very easily upload documents, e.g. with a drag-and-drop operation
- Separate sites have been set up for each work package and committee
- WP sites are maintained by the work packages themselves
- Committee sites are maintained by the project manager
- Each user (project participant) has a central “dashboard” that is accessed on initial login to the site and which provides an overview of all sites the user has access to (see Figure 4)
- If enabled by the individual user (on their dashboard) and/or for each WP site, activities on each site can be tracked (e.g. who made modifications or updates to documents to wikis, and when).
- Documents and other content are organised in a folder structure similar to e.g. Windows Explorer, so users do not have to get used to navigating around an unfamiliar set up (see Figure 5)
- A central site provides all project documentation and information to the partners; this site is maintained by the project manager (see Figure 6)
- Another central site provides dissemination and outreach material; this is maintained by the project manager and the outreach work package.

The screenshot shows the Alfresco user interface for Stephanie Suhr. The top navigation bar includes 'My Dashboard', 'Sites', 'People', 'Repository', and 'More...'. The main content area is divided into four panels:

- My Activities:** A list of recent actions, such as 'Wolfgang Kuchinke added document' and 'Astrid Woolard updated wiki page'.
- My Sites:** A list of sites created or managed by the user, including 'BioMedBridges partners' (with a list of documents like 'Description of Work', 'Planned resources', etc.), 'BioMedBridges people at EBI', 'BioMedBridges public documents', 'Dissemination activities and materials', 'Ethical Governance Committee', 'Executive Steering Committee', and 'Scientific Advisory Board'.
- BioMedBridges Google calendar:** A calendar view for December 2012, showing events like '2pm WPS' and '12pm BioM'.
- My Tasks:** A task list showing 'review the doc' as an 'Adhoc Task Completed, Completed'.

Figure 4 Example user dashboard in Alfresco for BioMedBridges

The screenshot displays the 'BioMedBridges partners' document library in Alfresco. The top navigation bar includes 'My Dashboard', 'Sites', 'People', 'Repository', and 'More...'. The main content area shows a list of documents organized into folders:

- BioMedBridges Grant Agreement, Description of Work, Consortium Agreement, Ethical Governance Framework** (Modified about a month ago by Stephanie Suhr)
- Contact lists** (Modified 11 days ago by Administrator)
- Deliverable reports (submitted)** (Modified 11 days ago by Stephanie Suhr)
- Deliverable templates** (Modified 11 days ago by Administrator)
- Kick-off meeting and AGMs (Presentations, minutes etc.)** (Modified 11 days ago by Stephanie Suhr)
- Project resources and timeline** (Modified about a month ago by Stephanie Suhr)
- Templates (Attendance lists, minutes, letters)** (Modified 11 days ago by Stephanie Suhr)

The left sidebar shows navigation options: 'Documents', 'Library', and 'Categories'. The bottom of the page features the 'Alfresco Enterprise' logo and copyright information.

Figure 5 Document library on the "BioMedBridges partners" site - documents can be easily organised e.g. via simple drag-and-drop operations

The screenshot displays the BioMedBridges partners site interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Alfresco logo and the site name 'BioMedBridges partners'. Below this, the main content area is divided into several sections:

- Wiki - Definition of terms used in the project - wiki:** This section includes 'Anonymisation' (explaining linked and unlinked data), 'Copyright' (describing automated rights), and 'Data' (referring to ethical governance terms).
- Site Profile:** Features a 'Welcome to BioMedBridges partners' message, a list of information and documentation, 'Site Manager(s): Administrator, Stephanie Suhr', and 'Visibility: Moderated'.
- Wiki - Partner RI affiliations:** A table listing partner institutions with columns for ID, acronym, name, and country.
- Site Links:** A list of project-related links such as 'BioMedBridges deliverables', 'BioMedBridges milestones', and various committees.
- Project calendar:** A calendar view for December 2012, showing dates from 25th to 31st.

Figure 6 "BioMedBridges partners" site with project documentation and information for all partners

Roles in Alfresco (and for the individual sites) have been assigned as follows:

Administrator: Full administration rights for overall site; role assigned to project manager and EBI external services only.

Site manager: Allows modifications to the set up of individual sites, including dashboard layout, inclusion of widgets etc. Assigned to one or more for each WP site, usually at least the WP leader.

Site collaborator: Can add, delete and modify/edit content of the respective site. Assigned to all members of a respective WP.

Site consumer: Can only "read" content from a site. Assigned to members of other WPs so they can read information on another WP site; Technical Coordination and Executive Steering Committee can read information on all project sites.

This setup enables the partners to freely share information with each other and also enables both the WPs to follow developments in other WPs as well as allowing the management bodies (Executive Steering and Technical Coordination Committee) to follow up on the overall project progress directly.

3.3.3 Tools and services domains

For technical reasons, separate domains will likely be set up for the tools and services developed within the project

1. The domains will be linked to the main BioMedBridges website (www.biomedbridges.eu), which will provide a “portal” to all services
2. The first domain includes a “BioMedBridges service registry” that lists data resources related to or necessary to accomplish the tasks of the project use cases, many of which are hosted by BioMedBridges partners
3. Tools and services domains are developed and maintained by the BioMedBridges technical staff (mostly WP4 technical integration).

5 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes X No

6 Adjustments made

No formal adjustments were made.

7 Efforts for this deliverable

Institute	Person-months (PM)		Period
	actual	estimated	
1: EMBL	12	12	April-December 2012
Total	12		

Background information

This deliverable relates to WP1; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP1 Title: Management
Lead: Janet Thornton, EMBL
Participants: n/a

The objectives of WP1 are the management of the BioMedBridges project, including organization of the management meetings such as the Annual General Meeting for all partners, the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum), and the meetings of the Scientific Advisory Committee, including reporting back to all partners. Among the tasks is also the provision of tools to ensure good communication between all partners, timely and appropriate reporting to the Commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages, development of metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community, the development of a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project and ensuring that any ethics issues that arise are addressed appropriately.

Work package number	WP1	Start date or starting event:				month 1
Work package title	Management					
Activity Type	MGT					
Participant number	1: EMBL	2: UOXF	3: KI	4: STFC	11: HMGU	13: VUMC
Person-months per participant	48	0	1	1	1	1

Objectives

1. To manage the BioMedBridges project from Year 1-4
2. To organise the management meetings for all the project including: the Annual General Meeting for all partners; the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum)
3. To organise the Scientific Advisory Committee and their annual meeting, including reporting back to all partners
4. To provide good communication between all partners, through a professional web site

5. To ensure timely and appropriate reporting to the commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages
6. To develop metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community
7. To develop with all partners a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project, following completion of the grant
8. To ensure that ethics issues are addressed

Description of work and role of participants

The project will be coordinated by Professor Janet Thornton at EMBL-EBI. The management structure will consist of an Executive Steering Committee, made up of the coordinators of the individual ESFRI BMS projects, and a Technical Coordination Committee, consisting of the Chairs and Co-chairs of the work packages. Janet Thornton will chair both committees. The Technical Coordination Committee will report to the Coordinator and Executive Steering Committee on a regular basis.

The tasks for this WP are as follows:

Task 1: Overall Coordination of the project The coordinator of BioMedBridges has full responsibility for managing this project and achieving its objectives, including infrastructure construction, project reporting and impact assessment and finance. The coordinator will be supported by a full time project manager, whose role will be to provide day-to-day support and implementation of all management and organisational tasks, including taking charge of accounting for all financial aspects of the project. The project manager will be responsible for the content management of the web site.

An Executive Steering Committee, consisting of all the coordinators of the 10 BMS Infrastructures, which are contributing to this grant. This committee, which is chaired by the BioMedBridges coordinator (who also coordinates the ELIXIR infrastructure), will play a strategic role in the management of the project and be responsible for decisions on the financial management. They will measure progress against the specific objectives, milestones and deliverables of each work package, developing metrics to measure the impact of the work. They will also ensure good coordination with the members of their own the infrastructure. They will oversee the consolidation of the data-infrastructure needs of the different projects, and develop a joint policy on these issues. They will monitor the sustainability of the components of the infrastructure being developed and develop a plan for support following the completion of this grant. The Executive Board will meet twice in the first year: a kick-off meeting and an ordinary Board meeting. In subsequent years, there would be annual meetings, as well as conference calls every two to three months. It is anticipated that the meetings would be held in connection with the Annual General Meetings where possible.

The Technical Coordination Committee will comprise the coordinator of the grant and scientists in charge of different aspects of the construction work with responsibility for coordinating one work package (ie the chairs and co-chairs of the different

construction Work Packages 1 - 5). The use case chairs will join this group as appropriate, during the tenure of their use case. This committee will therefore include technical experts taken from each infrastructure. This Committee has the responsibility to assess and report to the Executive Steering Committee on the progress of the work packages and to identify and prioritise future tasks for the following year. The chair for this committee will be the coordinator of the project. The Technical Coordination Committee will focus on the day-to-day and technical issues involved in achieving the planned deliverables and constructing the infrastructure. The Technical Coordination Committee will meet up to twice per year, in addition to the Annual General Meetings, and have monthly conference calls to deal with routine issues and resolve any urgent problems which may arise. The chairs and co-chairs of each Work Package will manage their own WP, ensuring good communication both within the WP and with the rest of this project, through this committee. This is described in more detail in the management section 2.1 below.

Task 2: Organisation of Management Meetings

The whole consortium will meet once a year at the Annual General Meetings. This meeting will involve all the partners and those employed and working on the grant. Presentations will be made on progress on each work package and the use cases described. In the first year there will be an additional meeting at the start of the grant, to ensure good coordination from the beginning. The AGMs would also be the main opportunity for the Executive Board and the Technical coordination Committee to meet and take joint decisions on the direction of the project, and for the advisory bodies (see below) to learn about the project and the progress being made, as well as providing strategic advice. The last AGM will be an open meeting, in part to provide outreach to all the members of each infrastructure, and also to ensure good uptake and exploitation of the deliverables of BioMedBridges. This meeting will be coordinated by WP2.

Task 3: Organisation of Scientific Advisory Board

The project will have two advisory bodies. We will construct a Scientific Advisory Board, which will comprise a small number of experts in the biological and biomedical life science infrastructure area. This will include world class biologists, IT experts, ethical and legal experts. In addition, representatives of the large e-infrastructures will be invited to form a Technology Watch e-Advisory Task Force, to keep the project informed on developments in this field and in general guarantee a close association between the ICT e-infrastructures and this project. The e-Advisory Task Force will form the Technology Watch Work Package (WP11), and consequently play a more integral part in the project than a conventional advisory board. It is anticipated that both advisory bodies would meet in connection with the Annual General Meetings.

Task 4: Provision of a professional web site

As well as providing the project with a public face, the project web site is also an important management tool. For this reason, the web site has been included in this work package, and will be based at EMBL-EBI, co-located with the coordinator and

project manager. The internal/restricted part of the web site will be used both as a workplace and as a repository of documents. The task here is to provide the technical infrastructure for the website, whose contents will be controlled by the project manager.

Task 5: Reporting on the Project to Commission

The project coordinator will be responsible for reporting to the commission, with help from the project manager. Reports from each work package will be delivered by the chair of that work package to the project coordinator, who will then combine these reports to deliver a coordinated report.

Task 6: Developing and monitoring progress and impact

The management bodies will develop procedures and metrics at the beginning of the grant to measure the progress of the grant and its impact on the biological and medical research communities. These metrics will be reported annually. All the partners involved in this WP will have responsibility for this task.

Task 7: Developing Sustainability Plan

During the course of the project the executive steering committee will monitor the sustainability of the infrastructure under construction. All the partners involved in this WP will have responsibility for this task. In the last year of the project the executive steering Committee will report on the long term sustainability of each component delivered.

Task 8: Establish an Ethical Governance Committee

The Ethical Governance Committee will:

- provide an ethics management report to each meeting of BioMedBridges Executive Steering Committee
- Analyse the requirements from the Ethics Review Report
- Review the draft Ethical Governance Framework document
- Monitor the compliance of the project beneficiaries with the Ethical Governance Framework
- Prepare new versions of the Ethical Governance Framework for approval by the Executive Steering Committee
- Support the External Independent Ethics Advisor in the preparation of Progress of Compliance with Ethics Requirements Reports.

Subcontracting for Audit Certificates: EMBL (Partner 1), STFC (Partner 4), UDUS (Partner 5), TUM-MED (Partner 7), TMF (Partner 10), HMGU (Partner 11), VUMC (Partner 13), UH (Partner 16).

Deliverables

No.	Name	Due month
D1.1	Website	12
D1.2	Devise metrics to measure progress and impact of construction	12
D1.3	1 st Periodic Report	18
D1.4	2 nd Periodic Report	36
D1.5	Final Report & Sustainability Plan	48
D1.6	ED1: The Ethical Governance Framework for BioMedBridges	18
D1.7	ED2: Progress of compliance with requirements of the Ethics Review Report	36
D1.8	ED3: External Independent Ethics Advisors Report	48